

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ADHITHYA A R 9SU20NS001**

has completed his/her minor project on **“Knowledge regarding Japanese Encephalitis among rural adults”** in the 2nd year BSc Nursing programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ABHIRAMI R 9SU20NS002**

has completed his/her minor project on **“Knowledge regarding Japanese Encephalitis among rural adults”** in the 2nd year BSc Nursing programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ADITHYA M P 9SU20NS004**

has completed his/her minor project on **“Knowledge regarding Japanese Encephalitis among rural adults”** in the 2nd year BSc Nursing programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **AJINA V V 9SU20NS007**

has completed his/her minor project on **“Knowledge regarding Japanese Encephalitis among rural adults”** in the 2nd year BSc Nursing programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ALBERT JOY 9SU20NS008**

has completed his/her minor project on **“Knowledge regarding Japanese Encephalitis among rural adults”** in the 2nd year BSc Nursing programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ALEENA SHIBU 9SU20NS009**

has completed his/her minor project on **“Knowledge regarding Japanese Encephalitis among rural adults”** in the 2nd year BSc Nursing programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ALEESHA K S 9SU20NS010**

has completed his/her minor project on **“Knowledge regarding Japanese Encephalitis among rural adults”** in the 2nd year BSc Nursing programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **AMISHA VARGHESE 9SU20NS011**

has completed his/her minor project on **“Knowledge regarding Japanese Encephalitis among rural adults”** in the 2nd year BSc Nursing programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **AMRITA FRANCIS 9SU20NS012**

has completed his/her minor project on **“Knowledge regarding Japanese Encephalitis among rural adults”** in the 2nd year BSc Nursing programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ANAMIKA P 9SU20NS014**

has completed his/her minor project on **“Knowledge regarding Japanese Encephalitis among rural adults”** in the 2nd year BSc Nursing programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ANJANA M 9SU20NS016**

has completed his/her minor project on **“Knowledge regarding Japanese Encephalitis among rural adults”** in the 2nd year BSc Nursing programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ANSU GEORGE 9SU20NS017**

has completed his/her minor project on **“Knowledge regarding Japanese Encephalitis among rural adults”** in the 2nd year BSc Nursing programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ANUSREE V C 9SU20NS018**

has completed his/her minor project on **“Knowledge regarding Japanese Encephalitis among rural adults”** in the 2nd year BSc Nursing programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **APARNA K 9SU20NS019**

has completed his/her minor project on **“Knowledge regarding Japanese Encephalitis among rural adults”** in the 2nd year BSc Nursing programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ASWATHI K K 9SU20NS021**

has completed his/her minor project on **“Knowledge regarding Japanese Encephalitis among rural adults”** in the 2nd year BSc Nursing programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ATHIRA RAJALAKSHMI 9SU20NS023**

has completed his/her minor project on **“Knowledge regarding Japanese Encephalitis among rural adults”** in the 2nd year BSc Nursing programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **BENCY BAISAL 9SU20NS025**

has completed his/her minor project on **“Knowledge regarding Japanese Encephalitis among rural adults”** in the 2nd year BSc Nursing programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **BESLIN GEORGE 9SU20NS026**

has completed his/her minor project on **“Knowledge regarding Japanese Encephalitis among rural adults”** in the 2nd year BSc Nursing programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **CYRIAC MANOJ VARGHESE 9SU20NS027**

has completed his/her minor project on **“Knowledge regarding Japanese Encephalitis among rural adults”** in the 2nd year BSc Nursing programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **FEBIN SAJI 9SU20NS029**

has completed his/her minor project on **“Knowledge regarding Japanese Encephalitis among rural adults”** in the 2nd year BSc Nursing programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **GLORIYA BENNY 9SU20NS030**

has completed his/her minor project on **“Knowledge regarding Japanese Encephalitis among rural adults”** in the 2nd year BSc Nursing programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **GLORIYA SHAIJU 9SU20NS031**

has completed his/her minor project on **“Knowledge regarding Japanese Encephalitis among rural adults”** in the 2nd year BSc Nursing programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **GOPIKA B S 9SU20NS032**

has completed his/her minor project on **“Knowledge regarding Japanese Encephalitis among rural adults”** in the 2nd year BSc Nursing programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **HARSHA K P 9SU20NS033**

has completed his/her minor project on **“Knowledge regarding Japanese Encephalitis among rural adults”** in the 2nd year BSc Nursing programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **HELLIN E 9SU20NS034**

has completed his/her minor project on **“Knowledge regarding Japanese Encephalitis among rural adults”** in the 2nd year BSc Nursing programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **HRIDYA ANEESH 9SU20NS035**

has completed his/her minor project on **“Knowledge regarding Japanese Encephalitis among rural adults”** in the 2nd year BSc Nursing programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **JASEELA M S 9SU20NS036**

has completed his/her minor project on **“Knowledge regarding Japanese Encephalitis among rural adults”** in the 2nd year BSc Nursing programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **JITHYA SAJI 9SU20NS037**

has completed his/her minor project on **“Knowledge regarding Japanese Encephalitis among rural adults”** in the 2nd year BSc Nursing programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **JYOTHIRMAYI K P 9SU20NS038**

has completed his/her minor project on **“Knowledge regarding Japanese Encephalitis among rural adults”** in the 2nd year BSc Nursing programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **KEERTHANA K 9SU20NS039**

has completed his/her minor project on **“Knowledge regarding Japanese Encephalitis among rural adults”** in the 2nd year BSc Nursing programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **KRITHIKA P K 9SU20NS040**

has completed his/her minor project on **“Knowledge regarding Japanese Encephalitis among rural adults”** in the 2nd year BSc Nursing programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **LAYANA MOHAN 9SU20NS042**

has completed his/her minor project on **“Knowledge regarding Japanese Encephalitis among rural adults”** in the 2nd year BSc Nursing programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MARIYA CLAISSON 9SU20NS043**

has completed his/her minor project on **“Knowledge regarding Japanese Encephalitis among rural adults”** in the 2nd year BSc Nursing programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **NAMITHA SAJU 9SU20NS044**

has completed his/her minor project on **“Knowledge regarding Japanese Encephalitis among rural adults”** in the 2nd year BSc Nursing programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MERIN M VARGHESE 9SU20NS045**

has completed his/her minor project on **“Knowledge regarding Japanese Encephalitis among rural adults”** in the 2nd year BSc Nursing programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **NANDANA O 9SU20NS047**

has completed his/her minor project on **“Knowledge regarding Japanese Encephalitis among rural adults”** in the 2nd year BSc Nursing programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **NIKHITHA K A 9SU20NS048**

has completed his/her minor project on **“Knowledge regarding Japanese Encephalitis among rural adults”** in the 2nd year BSc Nursing programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **NIVEDHYA SAJITH 9SU20NS049**

has completed his/her minor project on **“Knowledge regarding Japanese Encephalitis among rural adults”** in the 2nd year BSc Nursing programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **PARVATHY V S 9SU20NS050**

has completed his/her minor project on **“Knowledge regarding Japanese Encephalitis among rural adults”** in the 2nd year BSc Nursing programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **PILLAI KAVYA RADHAKRISHNAN**

08110016071

has completed his/her minor project on **“Knowledge regarding Japanese Encephalitis among rural adults”** in the 2nd year BSc Nursing programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **PUNYA P K 9SU20NS052**

has completed his/her minor project on **“Knowledge regarding Japanese Encephalitis among rural adults”** in the 2nd year BSc Nursing programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **RACHEL SHIJU 9SU20NS053**

has completed his/her minor project on **“Knowledge regarding Japanese Encephalitis among rural adults”** in the 2nd year BSc Nursing programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **RINSU ABRAHAM 9SU20NS054**

has completed his/her minor project on **“Knowledge regarding Japanese Encephalitis among rural adults”** in the 2nd year BSc Nursing programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SANDRA MATHEW 9SU20NS055**

has completed his/her minor project on **“Knowledge regarding Japanese Encephalitis among rural adults”** in the 2nd year BSc Nursing programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SHIKHA KRISHNA P 9SU20NS057**

has completed his/her minor project on **“Knowledge regarding Japanese Encephalitis among rural adults”** in the 2nd year BSc Nursing programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SNEHA SUKUMARAN 9SU20NS059**

has completed his/her minor project on **“Knowledge regarding Japanese Encephalitis among rural adults”** in the 2nd year BSc Nursing programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SREYA THERESA SEBASTIAN 9SU20NS061**

has completed his/her minor project on **“Knowledge regarding Japanese Encephalitis among rural adults”** in the 2nd year BSc Nursing programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SREYA V V 9SU20NS062**

has completed his/her minor project on **“Knowledge regarding Japanese Encephalitis among rural adults”** in the 2nd year BSc Nursing programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SWATHYMOL V S 9SU20NS064**

has completed his/her minor project on **“Knowledge regarding Japanese Encephalitis among rural adults”** in the 2nd year BSc Nursing programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **THEERTHA C 9SU20NS065**

has completed his/her minor project on **“Knowledge regarding Japanese Encephalitis among rural adults”** in the 2nd year BSc Nursing programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **RITHU MARY THOMAS 9SU20NS066**

has completed his/her minor project on **“Knowledge regarding Japanese Encephalitis among rural adults”** in the 2nd year BSc Nursing programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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